

Knowledge Business and Cultural Architecture (KBCA)

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Abstract

Businesses and Organisations incur in a myriad of business processes to perform their operations.

Enterprise Architecture captures all business operations. Business Processes can be modelled and documented to include the resources needed to perform them, but none of the most common methodologies used to implement Enterprise Architecture include the capability of capturing and modelling -in full detail- the knowledge required to perform specific tasks that make up the individual business processes.

In addition, Enterprise Architecture does not take into account cultural aspects when modelling business processes.

Example of a typical process model in Enterprise Architecture. A business process like „Taxi Order“ is composed of several individual tasks:

This proposed method expands the realm of the typical Enterprise Architecture by including Knowledge Management when modelling business processes.

Knowledge Business and Cultural Architecture (KBCA)

KBCA identifies two types of „knowledge properties“ to be captured in detail at the task level. Quantitative measurements are associated to these properties to concretely and objectively measure different indicators in detail.

Types of Knowledge Properties:

- **Business Operations:** to measure costs and type of knowledge.
- **Cultural Aspects:** to measure different types of cultural aspects, including demographics, geographic, age, gender, culture, etc

Quantitative Measurement of Knowledge associated to the business operations.

By identifying and assigning quantitative objective properties to the knowledge needed for a task, it is possible to measure quantitatively the value and impact of „Knowledge“ in business operations.

Business Knowledge Measurements:

- **Time**
Time to gain the knowledge about something. Time can be measured in Seconds, years, etc
- **# Resources**
it can be that to perform a specific task, more than one resource is needed. From this measurement additional information can be obtained, like Salary costs, type of job, demographics, etc.
- **Cost of acquisition**
the total costs incurred to obtain and maintain this knowledge.
- **Type**
to identify if the resource is human, animal, machine, spiritual or computer.

- Prerequisites?
 - operational: what is the cost of being healthy to perform the task? What is the cost of a machine to be operational?

Knowledge Measurements associated to Cultural and Demographic aspects

By identifying and assigning quantitative objective properties to the cultural aspects of the knowledge needed for a task, it is possible to measure quantitatively different cultural indicators associated.

- **Gender**
does this this knowledge apply to a particular gender only? is this task limited to a particular gender where it is performed?
- **Age**
from what age can you be a taxi driver where this task is performed? From what age is this knowledge needed or can be obtained in the particular context?
- **Geography**
Is this knowledge required only in a particular place? where or in what kind of geography can this task be performed? There might be places where this task is only performed by a certain gender. The reason would be also interesting to capture, if any. Measured by country, continent, etc.
- **Culture**
Is this knowledge required by a particular culture, tribe, etc.? Are there cultures that would not perform this task? Which cultures have performed this task?
- **Epoch**
is this knowledge needed in a particular Epoch? Like Middle ages, 21st century

Example

Business: Taxi company
 Business Process: Taxi Order
 Task: Perform transportation
 Price of the ride: 20Eur (18 + 2 Tip)
 Operational costs ?

Business Properties	Value
Time	10 years. it should include the time required to learn how to drive, time required to be taxi driver, a particular vehicle with all the gadgets, to drive in a particular environment, etc.
Cost	5000EUR. how much in total has it costed in context to be to the point of the driver taking this job of driving this customer to his or her destination?
Resources	3 see type
Type	Human, Machine and Computer. It might be that the driver is communicating with the taxi company per radio, or with a navigation computer via satellite.
Cultural Properties	Value
Age	18
Gender	Any
Geography	USA
Culture	Western. But pretty much any culture will order a taxi if they could.
Epoch	to what age in time does this task belong? Since when can one order a taxi in the usa?

Conclusion

The benefits of this methodology are:

1. Visibility of the knowledge needed in detail for specific tasks
2. Ability to measure the knowledge needed in detail for specific tasks
3. Identification of the cultural aspects of the knowledge needed in detail for specific tasks

References

Enterprise Architecture, Wikipedia https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Enterprise_architecture